

Polarographic Reduction of Uranyl and Thorium Complexes of Methyl-3-Mercaptopropionate

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The polarographic reduction of UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} ions in Methyl-3-mercaptopropionate has been found to be irreversible and diffusion controlled in 0.1 M NaClO_4 , 0.002% Triton X-100 and 25% ethanol. The values of kinetic parameters-transfer coefficient (α), formal rate constant ($k_{f,h}^0$) for the electrode reaction are determined by Koutecky's method as extended by Meites and Israel. The free energy, enthalpy and entropy of activation have also been reported.

METHYL-3-mercaptopropionate belongs to an important class of organo sulphur compounds which have applications in biological, pharmaceutical and industrial fields. Polarographic behaviour of organo sulphur compounds and their metal complexes have been studied extensively in these laboratories by Saxena and co-workers¹⁻⁵. This communication reports the polarographic reduction of uranyl and thorium ions in presence of methyl-3 mercaptopropionate for which there is no reference in the literature.

Experimental

The capillary of the manual polarograph, with scalamp galvanometer as current recorder and S.C.E. as reference electrode, had the following characteristics in 25% ethanol, 0.1 M NaClO_4 at -0.5 V with h_{Hg} value of 40 cm; $m=2.895$ mg/sec, $t=2.39$ sec.

The nature of the waves produced by uranyl and thorium ions in methyl-3-mercaptopropionate (referred herein as RSH) was investigated by studying the effects of change in Hg-pressure and temperature on the wave height. The values of kinetic parameters were determined from the polarograms of the solutions containing 1.0 mM UO_2^{2+} (in 0.01 M HClO_4) or 0.1 mM Th^{4+} , 0.1 M NaClO_4 , 0.002% Triton X-100, 25% ethanol and different amounts of RSH. The current was recorded at the end of the drop life instead of average current as the determination of kinetic parameters is based on Koutecky's method which are accurately reproduced by measuring the maximum current.

Results and Discussion

The conventional log plots of the reduction waves for UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} ions in methyl-3-mercaptopropionate were straight lines but their slopes were

not in agreement with the theoretical values for the reversible waves, indicating the irreversible nature of the waves in both the systems. The value of n , number of electrons involved in the reduction process was determined by millicoulometric method of De-Vries and Kroon⁶ using a mercury pool cathode and found to be 2 and 4 in the case of UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} respectively.

Linear variation of the diffusion current (i_d) with the square root of height of the mercury column ($h_{\text{eff}}^{1/2}$) in each case and the values of temperature coefficients for i_d (0.6376% per deg. for UO_2^{2+} -RSH and 2.30% per deg. for Th^{4+} -RSH system) indicate the diffusion-controlled nature of the waves. With increase in [RSH], the $E_{1/2}$ shifts towards more negative potential showing the complex formation between metal ions and the ligand, whereas i_d decreases for UO_2^{2+} system and increases for Th^{4+} system indicating that the aquo-uranyl and aquo-thorium ions differ in size from their complexes of RSH.

Since UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} ions reduce irreversibly in presence of RSH, it is considered expedient to determine the kinetic parameters, transfer coefficient (α) and formal rate constant ($k_{f,h}^0$), for the electrode reaction by applying Koutecky's theoretical treatment⁷ as extended by Meties and Israel⁸ which is based on the plot of $E_{d,e}$ vs. $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$.

For an irreversible cathodic wave it follows that :

$$E_{d,e} = -0.2412 + \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 k_{f,h}^0 t^{1/2}}{D_o^{1/2}} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} \log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$$

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which may be rewritten as

$$E_{d,e} = E_{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} \log \frac{i}{i_d - i} \quad (1)$$

with

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}} = -0.2412 + \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 k^{\circ} t_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{3}} f_{f,h}}{D_o^{\frac{1}{3}}} \quad (2)$$

The enthalpy of activation (ΔH^{\ddagger}) for the electrode reaction has been calculated by equating the

slope of $\log k^{\circ}_{f,h}$ vs. $\frac{1}{T}$ plot to $\frac{-\Delta H^{\ddagger}}{(2.303R)}$ and

found to be 5.4 KCal/mole for UO_2^{2+} -system at 25° and 7.8 Kcal/mole for Th^{4+} system at 35°. The

TABLE 1—VALUES OF D_o , αn AND $k^{\circ}_{f,h}$ AT VARIOUS [RSH] FOR UO_2^{2+} AND Th^{4+} SYSTEMS.

	Conc. of RSH (mM)	i_d (μA)	$-E_{1/2}$ (volts)	$D_o \times 10^6$	αn	$k^{\circ}_{f,h}$ (cm/sec)
UO_2^{2+} (mM) Temp. 20°	2	2.04	0.4510	2.046	0.733	3.6×10^{-6}
	4	1.86	0.4200	1.701	0.702	3.5×10^{-6}
	6	1.62	0.4245	1.290	0.697	2.8×10^{-6}
Th^{4+} (0.1mM) Temp. 30°	2	2.24	1.1950	0.154	0.929	1.5×10^{-18}
	4	2.48	1.2040	0.189	0.903	3.3×10^{-18}
	6	2.80	1.2100	0.241	0.813	9.0×10^{-18}

The values of kinetic parameters for the present systems were calculated with the help of equations (1) and (2). The values of αn was obtained by

equating the slope of $E_{d,e}$ vs. $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ plot to $-\frac{0.0542}{\alpha n}$ and the intercept of the same plot ($E_{1/2}$)

was used to calculate $k^{\circ}_{f,h}$. The values of $D_o^{\frac{1}{3}}$ was determined from Ilkovic equation. Since it does not vary appreciably over the range of potential

free energy of activation (ΔG^{\ddagger}), determined from the

relation $k^{\circ}_{f,h} = \frac{KT}{h} \exp \left(\frac{-\Delta G^{\ddagger}}{RT} \right)$ is found to

be 15.6 Kcal/mole for UO_2^{2+} and 35.5 Kcal/mole for Th^{4+} system. The entropy of activation, calculated from the relation

$$\Delta S^{\ddagger} = \frac{\Delta H^{\ddagger} - \Delta G^{\ddagger}}{T}$$

is -34.0 cal/deg/mole for UO_2^{2+} and -76.8 cal/deg/mole for Th^{4+} -system.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF D_o , αn AND $k^{\circ}_{f,h}$ FOR UO_2^{2+} -RSH AND Th^{4+} -RSH SYSTEM AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES.

	Temp (°C)	i_d (μA)	$-E_{1/2}$ (volts)	Temp. coeff. (% per deg)	$D_o \times 10^6$	αn	$k^{\circ}_{f,h}$ (cm/sec)
UO_2^{2+} -RSH system	20	2.04	0.4150	—	2.046	0.733	3.6×10^{-6}
	25	2.18	0.4070	0.5806	2.169	0.752	4.1×10^{-6}
	30	2.26	0.4010	0.6656	2.337	0.769	4.6×10^{-6}
	35	2.34	0.3940	0.6677	2.512	0.774	5.8×10^{-6}
Th^{4+} -RSH system	30	2.48	1.2040	—	0.189	0.903	3.3×10^{-18}
	35	2.80	1.1950	2.428	0.241	0.903	5.1×10^{-18}
	40	3.12	1.830	2.296	0.299	0.910	6.4×10^{-18}
	45	3.44	1.650	2.178	0.363	0.929	7.3×10^{-18}

covered by the rising part of the wave, it was considered unnecessary to apply the correction for drop-time.

Table 1 shows that the values of αn and $k^{\circ}_{f,h}$ are affected by the concentration of the ligand because of the change in $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ and i_d . Increase in $k^{\circ}_{f,h}$ with temperature indicates that the rate of electrode process for UO_2^{2+} -RSH and Th^{4+} -RSH systems increases with temperature (Table 2). Shift in half-wave potential towards more positive value shows the easier reduction of the complexes at higher temperatures and is in accordance with the irreversible nature of the electrode process.

References

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